

REPORT:

A3.1.1: Review of the microfluidic devices, components on the market

Work package 3

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Activity number	Activity description	Participants (Lead in bold)
A3.1.1 M3	UofG in collaboration with LEI, CETIAT, IPQ, INESC MN, RISE, DTI and PTB will carry out a comprehensive review and inventory of the cutting-edge microfluidic devices, components (tubing, connectors, vacuum connectors, microfluidic devices) currently available on the market. Information from A2.1.1 (by M3) and A2.1.2 (by M3) will complement this review. DTI will include all the information collected into the EMPIR 20NRM02 MFMET database, expanding it.	UofG , LEI, CETIAT, IPQ, INESC MN, RISE, DTI, PTB

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1. Scope

This document summarises previous reviews of microfluidic devices and components and provides updates on emerging commercial microfluidic devices, with a focus on those intended for biological applications.

2. Review

2.1 Summary of materials used for microfluidic devices and components

One of the fundamental steps in microfluidic applications is selecting the optimum material for device fabrication. Since, on a microscale surface, the properties are much more amplified, the platform material is likely to affect the properties of synthesized nanomaterials. Specifically, unique phenomena emerge in capillary microfluidics due to shorter retention times, laminar flows, enhanced heat and mass transfer, and large surface-to-volume ratios. Unlike macroscale vessels, the wetting and contact angles of an aqueous solution on the chip materials are of fundamental importance. Other essential properties that must be considered when choosing the material are durability, ease of fabrication, transparency, biocompatibility, chemical compatibility with the implied reagents, meeting the temperature and pressure conditions needed for the reaction, and the potential of the surface functionalization.

Various kinds of materials attempt to match these properties and can be used for the manufacturing of microfluidic devices. Typical substrates include glass, silicon, metals, polymers, and ceramics, but the diversity and quality of materials are continuously increasing. Each material has both advantages and disadvantages, depending on its destination use [1].

EMPIR 20NRM02 MFMET reviewed common microfluidic devices available on the market, including their materials, fabrication, connection and integrations. The information was included in the following deliverables:

- White Paper on common microfluidic components materials: properties and fabrication [2].
- D5 20NRM02 MFMET - Guidelines for the measurement of key performance parameters of microfluidic connections including the identification of key properties in an interface [3].
- D6 20NRM02 MFMET - Guidelines for the implementation of standardised methods of microfluidic components focusing on port connection from microscale fluidic channels to the macroscale world and associated changes in flow and pressure [4].
- D7 20NRM02 MFMET - Landscape document identifying standardization requirements for microfluidic component design and manufacturing with respect to modularity and heterogenous integration [5].

Here, we will summarise key recommendations from these documents and expand on information about material properties that are relevant for biological applications.

Base materials commonly used for manufacturing microfluidic devices include: cycloolefin copolymer (COC), copolyester thermoplastic elastomer (COP), polycarbonate (PC), polystyrene (PS), silicon, ceramics and glass.

COC/COP is mainly used for disposables Point-of-Care testing devices. PC and PS are popular choices for cell cultures or organ-on-chip devices. Glass is especially used in demanding applications that are reused frequently and for long periods of time and/or operates at higher pressures and temperatures. Less often used materials include Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and silicon.

Materials commonly used for connectors and tubing include: Polypropylene (PP), PS, silicone, perfluoroelastomer (FFKM), stainless steel and fused silica.

For biological applications, the biocompatibility, temperature range for continuous use, gas permeabilities and suitable sterilisation methods of a material must be considered. Such information is included for these commonly used materials (Table 1).

Table 1. The relevant properties of common materials for biological applications

Material name	Biocompatibility	Temperature range	Gas permeabilities	Method for sterilisation
COC	Good	Up to ~100 °C	Very low	EtO, gamma, not autoclavable
COP	Good	Up to ~100 °C	Very low	EtO, gamma, not autoclavable
PC	Good	Up to ~120 °C	Moderate	Limited Autoclave, Gamma, EtO,
PMMA	Moderate	Up to ~70–90 °C	Low	EtO, gamma (not autoclavable)
PP	Good	Up to ~100 °C	Low	Autoclave, Gamma, EtO
PS	Moderate	Up to ~70–90 °C	Moderate	Gamma, EtO (not autoclavable)
Silicone	Excellent	–60 °C to 200 °C	Very high	Autoclave, EtO
FFKM	Excellent	–20 °C to 260 °C	low	Autoclave, chemical sterilisation
stainless steel	Excellent	Up to ~400 °C	Impermeable	Autoclave, chemical sterilisation
Fused silica	Excellent	Up to ~1000 °C	Impermeable	Autoclave, chemical sterilisation
Glass	Excellent	Up to ~1000 °C	Impermeable	Autoclave, chemical sterilisation
Silicon	Excellent	Up to ~1000 °C	Impermeable	Autoclave, chemical sterilisation

Representative devices can be found in Table 2.

Table 2. Examples of organ-on-a-chip companies and devices.

Name	Representative devices	website
Emulate, Inc.	A range of organ-chips (lung, liver, kidney, intestine, brain etc.) 96-chip system	https://emulatebio.com
MIMETAS B.V.	OrganoPlate® platform for 3D human tissue culture under perfusion, 96-chip system	https://www.mimetas.com/technology
TissUse GmbH	Multi-Organ-Chips for predicting toxicity ADME profiles and efficacy in vitro	https://www.tissuse.com/en/about-us
CN Bio Innovations Ltd.	PhysioMimix® Core Microphysiological System	https://cn-bio.com/about
Kirkstall Ltd	Quasi-Vivo® flow-based cell culture systems	https://kirkstall.com
BEOnChip S.L.	Microfluidic “organ-on-chip” devices aimed at biomimetic environments	https://beonchip.com
BiomimX	uBeat® Platform supports the culture of 3D microtissues within a single device.	https://www.biomimx.com/products
Microfluidic chipshop	Manufacturer of various microfluidic devices	https://www.microfluidic-chipshop.com

2.2 Microfluidic devices and components for biological applications

Microfluidic devices are increasingly used in molecular diagnostics and cell-based assays, including high throughput single cell analysis and organ-on-a-chip models. A range of commercial products are listed in Annex Table 1. Since most of these applications involve on-chip detection, excellent optical properties of a device (e.g., transparency and low autofluorescence) are essential. Other factors,

including biocompatibility, gas permeability, adsorption, chemical and thermal stability, and the sterilisation methods, should be considered depending on the intended applications.

Similar to traditional disposable plastic wares, microfluidic devices for biological assays may be single use to avoid contamination. Therefore, materials suitable for scalable manufacture are critical to ensure affordability and low costs.

With the advancement of technology, microfluidic technology has undergone tremendous development and has been widely applied in the field of biology. Microfluidic biomaterials combine microfluidic technology and biomaterial science, with the core of designing, preparing, or regulating the physical and chemical properties of biomaterials through micro/nanoscale fluid manipulation technology to achieve precise control of their performance. The channel width in microfluidic biomaterials requires more precise accuracy than millimeter level. Microfluidic biomaterials are porous at multiple length scales, where one characterizes the channel width and the other characterizes the average pore size of the biomaterial block. The most common microfluidic biomaterials are hydrogels, such as alginate or type I collagen [6].

Base materials used for biological applications

COC/COP are the most popular materials for biological use microfluidic devices due to their transparency, low adsorption, manufacturability, and regulatory acceptance.

Devices for molecular diagnostics (such as genotyping and RNA sequencing) are often made from COC/COP, for example Fluidigm's Integrated Fluidic Circuits (Standard Biotools) or Microfluidic ChipShop's fluidic chips.

Hydrogels are colloidal networks or cross-linked polymer networks in which the swelling agent is water. Due to their high biocompatibility and similarity to the extracellular matrix of organisms, hydrogels have been extensively studied for biomedical applications. Recently, micrometer-sized hydrogels with dimensions ranging from several to hundreds of micrometers have been developed to take advantage of both hydrogels and micrometer-sized carriers. Specifically, microgels can be injected through tiny needles without additional modification, which is beneficial for the delivery of drugs or cells. Most micrometer-sized hydrogels are inherently modular since multiple micrometer-sized hydrogel systems with different chemical compositions or dimensions can create various materials for diverse applications.

Devices involving cell-culture on chip (e.g., organ-on-a-chip) are often made from hybrid materials to meet different requirements (Annex Table 1). For example:

- Mimetis OrganoPlates are made of COC with a glass bottom to provide optical transparency.
- Microfluidic ChipShop Fluidic 480 device consists of a membrane sandwiched between two PS plates with channels/chambers, where the membrane supports cell growth. This two-layered 3D structure is essential for generating dynamic flow conditions in tissue models. Various organ-on-a-chip devices adopted similar approaches.
- Some tissues also require mechanical stretching to reproduce in vivo-like phenotypes. For instance, Emulate's stretchable organ-chip, made from PDMS, provide excellent elastic properties that enable delivery of such mechanical cues.

Connectors and tubing

As discussed in D6 and D7 20NRM02 MFMET, one of the biggest technical hurdles in the performance of microfluidic devices is the microfluidic interface, especially when connecting to external

instruments via tubing. Tubing connections are difficult for biologists to handle, and cells are prone to sedimentation in long and narrow tubing, which complicates delivering cell solutions to a chip. While large, standardized interfaces such as Luer fittings can alleviate some of these issues, “tubeless” operation remains ideal for end users. Increasingly, automated organ-on-a-chip systems integrate pipetting interfaces and microtiter format with fluidic modules.

2.3 Microfluidic devices and components for high-vacuum applications

Leak detection of microfluidic devices as a means of quality control can be carried out using a leak detector operated in high vacuum. A tracer gas, usually helium, is applied to one side of the device while the other is kept under vacuum. The leak rate of helium entering the vacuum side is measured with the leak detector.

To maintain a high vacuum within the device, connectors must be used that are reasonably leak tight. This can be achieved using a threaded fitting with an elastomer ferrule that seals against a rigid tubing, e.g. VacuTight fittings from IDEX. Soft elastic tubing must not be used as the pressure difference between the ambient pressure outside of the tube and the vacuum inside would cause the tube to collapse.

When performing a leak test under high vacuum conditions in the molecular flow regime, the transport of helium along the tube can be envisioned as a one-dimensional diffusion process with the characteristic length given by the diameter of the tube. To keep response times short, long tubing and small inner diameters shall be avoided.

2.4 Integrated microfluidic devices for biological applications

Integration of microfluidic devices with sensors, actuators and fluidic controls is essential for a wide range of applications that require miniaturisation, automation, and real-time monitoring. The MFMET II A2.1.2 report summarises the current integration strategies. This section focuses on their potential and limitations in biological applications involving cell culture, such as organ-on-chip devices.

Monolithically fabricated devices can integrate multiple functionalities within a single substrate, offering high alignment accuracy and compact footprints. However, this often requires combining different materials within the same device. The resulting fabrication processes are not only costly but also restrict the range of functionalities that can be incorporated simultaneously. For example, while TEER testing is routinely performed in standard well-plate formats, OoC devices with integrated TEER measurement capabilities are still under development in research labs [7-8].

Hybrid and Modular Integration strategies combine individual components such as sensors, actuators, and fluidic modules together through techniques like anodic bonding, adhesive bonding, or thermal bonding. This approach allows the integration of diverse functionalities, but has to meet demanding requirements for precise alignments, reliable interconnections, and low dead volumes. Recently, Additive Manufacturing Techniques [9], such as 3D printing, have enabled the integration of complex fluidic networks with embedded sensors and actuators in a single build process, although issues such as resolution limits and material compatibility still pose challenges. Regardless of the fabrication strategies, the chosen sterilisation method must be suitable for all components. Features prone to generating bubbles and trapping cells, such as rough surface and large dead volumes, should be minimised or eliminated.

On the other hand, microfluidic devices can be directly connected via tubing and fittings to commercially available sensors and flow generators. A2.1.1 lists commonly used commercial pumps and sensors along with their specifications and connector types. Although this approach does not

produce a compact, fully integrated device, the use of off-the-shelf components offers advantages in accessibility, robustness, reusability of expensive elements (e.g. Sensors), and flexibility of sterilisation methods for different components.

3. Conclusions

This report updates the reviews from EMPIR 20NRM02 MFMET project on common available microfluidic devices, with a focus on their materials, fabrication, connection and integration relevant for biological applications involving cell-culture on chip (e.g., organ-on-chip).

When selecting materials, considerations such as biocompatibility, temperature range for continuous use, gas permeabilities, and suitable sterilisation methods are essential. Information of commonly used materials is provided in this report.

For devices integrating functional modules (such as sensors) or connected to individual components, issues such as cell sedimentation, bubble generation, operational difficulty, and sterilisation must be considered throughout design and fabrication. Similar to plastic well plates, OoC devices could be disposable, which impose challenges for fabrication cost and affordability.

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